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Correlating crack density, stiffness degradation and dissipated energy during fatigue loading of $\pm 45^\circ$ GFRP laminates

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Fatigue of composites

Progressive fatigue damage model for Stage I

→ Predicts stiffness degradation based on crack density

Experimental characterization for calibration

→ Quantification of crack density and resulting mechanical properties

K. L. Reifsneider "Fatigue of Composite Materials". no. 4 in Composite materials series, Elsevier, 1991.

M. Drvoderic, M. Pletz, C. Schuecker "Modeling Stiffness Degradation of Fiber-Reinforced Polymers Based on Crack Densities Observed in Off-Axis Plies". Journal of Composite Science, Vol. 6, No. 1, 2021.

Fatigue characterization

- Crack density

→ Automated crack detection with open-source software **CrackDect**

$$\rho = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n l_i}{A}$$

l_i length of the i^{th} crack
 A area of interest

- Stiffness degradation

- Dissipated energy

Material has to be semi-transparent:

±45° glass-epoxy laminate

Testing procedure

Cyclic loading blocks:

- Dissipated energy

Quasi-static tensile tests:

➔ Interruption of cyclic loading after defined intervals

- Stiffness
- Crack density

Stiffness / crack density

- Stiffness decrease and crack initiation happen simultaneously
- Higher load levels \rightarrow earlier start of stiffness degradation / crack initiation
- Off-axis cracks grow in number and size over the fatigue life
- Crack growth rate slows down when diffuse delamination starts to occur

Data marked with Δ are published in: M. Drvoderic, M. Gfrerrer, J. Wiener, G. Pinter, M. Pletz, C. Schuecker "Comparing crack density and dissipated energy as measures for off-axis damage in composite laminates". International Journal of Fatigue, Vol. 169, 107486, 2023.

Crack density / dissipated energy

fatigue tests $\pm 45^\circ$ GFRP laminates
 $R = 0.1, f = 3 \text{ Hz}$

- Higher load levels \rightarrow earlier increase of dissipated energy
- Dissipated energy...
 - ... increases later in time compared to crack density
 - ... continues to increase after crack saturation
 - \rightarrow Result of other mechanisms (e.g. delamination) or internal friction
 - \rightarrow Not a good measure for off-axis damage

Detected cracks at a load level of 0.65:

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Fatigue characterization with acoustic emission

New test series with different laminate:

- Crack density
- Stiffness degradation
- Dissipated energy
- **Acoustic emission (AE)**

... optical crack detection is limited to semi-transparent laminates

AE as alternative method for crack detection applicable to non-transparent materials?

Fatigue characterization with acoustic emission

1st series

UD glass fabric (10% weft yarns) + epoxy matrix

Cyclic loading + tensile tests

→ Classic Young's modulus

Good correlation of quasi-static modulus and dynamic modulus was found

2nd series

UD glass-epoxy prepreg

Reduction of test complexity: Cyclic loading

→ Dynamic modulus from hysteresis

M. Drvoderic, M. Gfrerrer, J. Wiener, G. Pinter, M. Pletz, C. Schuecker "Comparing crack density and dissipated energy as measures for off-axis damage in composite laminates". International Journal of Fatigue, Vol. 169, 107486, 2023.

Stiffness / crack density / AE events

No crack saturation

Cumulative AE events significantly increase later in time compared to crack density

➔ Result of other mechanisms (e.g. delamination) or internal friction

More AE events detected for lower load levels

➔ higher number of cycles

➔ more AE signals due to friction

Stiffness / crack density / AE events

First detected AE signals correlate with
crack initiation

Conclusion

Correlation of crack density with

- **Stiffness degradation**

- Stiffness decrease and crack initiation happen simultaneously

- **Dissipated energy (hysteresis loops)**

- Increases later in time compared to crack density
- Continues to increase after crack saturation

- **AE events**

- Significantly increase later in time compared to crack density
- More AE events detected for lower load levels
- Crack initiation can be detected (depends on AE measuring parameters)

Result of other mechanisms
or internal friction

Higher number of cycle
More signals due to friction

Detailed analysis of AE signal parameters: Differentiation between source mechanisms?

CrackDect

**Crack Density
Comparison**

Thank You!
